

**PSYCHOEDUCATIONAL PROGRAM AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL IN DEVELOPING THE
LEADERSHIP QUALITIES OF THE FUTURE TEACHER**

Lohvys O.

*practical psychologist of the department for youth affairs, assistant at the Department of Developmental
Psychology and Counseling,*

Ternopil Volodymyr Hnatiuk National Pedagogic University, Ternopil

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Abstract

The article analyses the presents considerations regarding the need for the formation and development of leadership qualities in future teachers in a higher education institution. Especially in modern conditions, it is very important to develop the leadership qualities of teachers. The transformation of education today calls for a new generation teacher - not just someone who will transfer knowledge and teach, but a facilitator in the child's educational trajectory, a mentor, a coach and a mentor. That is why the role of the teacher-leader is a conceptual point of the National Strategy for the Development of Education in Ukraine and the concept of the New Ukrainian School. Actually, this involves "ensuring the personal development of a person according to his individual abilities and needs based on lifelong learning", and the strategic direction is the reform of the education system based on the principle of the priority of the person [2, 4, 13].

Keywords: leadership qualities, future teachers, facilitation, subject-subject interaction, subjectivity, reflexivity, flexibility, emotional intelligence, empathy, internality

The defining features of leadership in education are: direct contact between the leader and his followers, the diversity of educational leadership, the presence of leadership qualities in both the heads of the educational institution and other participants, the ability to educate leaders. Researchers draw attention to the important role of the teacher's personality in the life of the future generation and in promoting their personal growth. That is why the concept of higher education today provides for the development of a leadership position in the subject-subject interaction of participants in the educational process [4, 6, 8].

A modern pedagogue-leader is called upon to be, first of all, a facilitator, whose main tasks are: involvement in the full participation of the subjects of the educational process, promoting mutual understanding, stimulating the adoption of a mutually acceptable decision, cultivating a sense of joint responsibility [13, 15].

In the process of such subject-subject interaction, co-action, coexistence in the "teacher-student" system, the teacher-leader often becomes an ideal for his students, thus forming a desire to become like him. That is why he must possess certain leadership qualities: confidence in himself and his pupils, pedagogical optimism, readiness for innovative changes, a desire for self-development and self-improvement, the ability to create a favorable educational environment for the development of his pupils and the formation of leadership qualities in them [8].

The following domestic scientists contributed to the development of research on leadership qualities: O. Bandurka, S. Bocharova, O. Vikhanskyi, O. Zhuravlyova, E. Zemlianska, T. Kabachenko, S. Kalashnikova, A. Mitlosh, V. Milyaeva, O. Nestulya, S. Novikova, O. Romanovsky, V. Sal'yakhov, N. Semchenko, V. Spivakovsky and others. Understanding the concept of leadership qualities of students of higher education institutions and their structure is considered in the works of B. Goloveshko, K.

Demchuk, A. Zorina, I. Krasnoshchok, N. Marakhovska, R. Sopivnyk, and others. According to E. Zharikov and E. Krushelnytskyi, a person's ability to be a leader largely depends on the development of his organizational and communicative qualities [7, 10].

Considering the specificity of our research, it is advisable to refer to the structure of the teacher's professional activity in order to find out what qualities a teacher-leader should possess. The issue of the teacher's leadership role was dealt with by A. Baldwin, Yu. Hilbukh, I. Ivanov, J. Ketten, O. Kyrychuk, K. Clark, Ya. Kolomynskyi, N. Marakhovska, N. Semchenko, L. Termen et al. Studying various aspects of pedagogical leadership, these researchers emphasized the importance of the formation of the general and pedagogical culture of the individual, the development of leadership abilities and skills in the process of professional activity [5, 8, 10].

Summarizing the opinions of various authors, we conclude that leadership qualities are defined as "personal factors that manifest both in the context of professional work and outside of it. These are internal traits or abilities that enable the leader to act effectively, while contributing to the development of the organization".

The relevance of the study of the problem of leadership qualities of future teachers in the process of professional training is explained by the fact that a teacher must be, first of all, a leader for himself, a facilitator, an organizer, a mentor of student and parent teams. Pedagogical activity obliges him to reveal and develop his own leadership qualities and prepare leaders of the school team. The results of the study of the peculiarities of the development of leadership qualities in the process of personal and professional formation of the future teacher showed that leadership qualities represent a dynamic professional and personal formation that is formed in the process of professional training in a pedagogical institution of higher education [13].

Therefore, our research presents a model of the integral structure of a teacher's leadership qualities from the point of view of the psychology of pedagogical activity and the paradigm of leadership in education. As a result of studying the psychological and pedagogical literature on the selected topic, we singled out the four most important, in our opinion, components of this structure: motivational-value, emotional-communicative, organizational-regulatory and reflective-evaluative.

The motivational and value component of a teacher's leadership qualities is represented by such qualities as professional motivation, the desire for self-actualization, and orientation to the teacher's humanistic values. The emotional-communicative component is manifested in indicators of emotional intelligence, communicative inclinations, empathy, openness and flexibility in communication. Organizational-regulatory is a tendency to leadership, the level of self-regulation, organizational inclinations and an indicator of internality. And positive self-attitude, reflexivity and the need for self-development are revealed reflexive and evaluative component of the structure of leadership qualities of the future teacher [11].

These and other important qualities of a teacher-leader undoubtedly need to be developed both in the process of subject-subject interaction during the educational process and within the framework of informal education. Taking into account the above, we believe that the process of training future teachers in institutions of higher education from the position of leadership in education should be considered in more detail. Therefore, we set ourselves the goal of developing and testing a psycho-educational development program that would contribute to the development of leadership qualities in future teachers. We consider the consideration of the forms, methods and techniques of psychological and pedagogical influence, which will be carried out from the standpoint of student-centrism, to be a determining factor in this search.

The leadership qualities of a future teacher can be developed in the educational space of a higher education institution, in the process of professional training. In our opinion, we consider the use of such a psychodidactic technology as "educational dialogue" to be effective from the point of view of promoting the development of leadership qualities in the process of subject-subject interaction. After all, dialogue acts as a way of life of subjects in education, it is through it that the teacher can intervene in the meaning-seeking process of the student [12].

According to G. Radchuk, educational dialogue is a form of active learning, the purpose of which is the assimilation of professional knowledge at the value-meaning level, and at the same time as a form of communication in which the problems of personality development are solved, providing psychological support to it, which allows to debunk stereotypes and solve personal problems of participants, to form skills of social interaction. As an innovative psychodidactic technology, he involves the organization of the joint cognitive activity of the teacher and the student at the value-meaning level, the full inclusion of students in

the educational process and the actualization of their subject potential [10].

As noted by G. Radchuk, the student's readiness for dialogic communication includes: his internal motivation, relative autonomy, internality, the need for self-development, reflexivity, self-respect and situational self-actualization [9]. We singled out these qualities among the list included in the integral structure of leadership qualities necessary for the teacher to implement. Therefore, the dialogic nature of the teacher in the Concept of the New Ukrainian School is the basis of partnership interaction between subjects of the educational process [6].

According to G. Radchuk, the main principles of organizing cognitive activity in the form of educational dialogue are: the principle of acquiring personal experience through the actualization of meaningful experiences in the learning process; interaction in conditions of uncertainty; authorship as a condition of cognitive activity; incompleteness of dialogue as a method of knowledge; multi-aspect, alternative, multi-positional knowledge; the principle of openness [9].

Understanding education as meaningful, "authorial", we consider the educational dialogue as the starting point of the student's personal transformation. The essence of "dialogization" as a factor in the development of the subject's position consists, first of all, in overcoming the traditional antagonisms of education, namely, the executive position of the student in the educational situation, the passive position of the teacher in the development of intersubjective interaction, the reproductive nature of assimilation of educational information and initiating preparation of an active, capable of independent development and adoption of non-standard decisions of the future specialist [11, 14].

As G. Radchuk notes, the dialogic process in education can be presented at the level of formal dialogue as a form of communication between the subjects of the educational process, at the level of substantive dialogue that reflects the dialogic nature of educational material, at the level of personal-semantic dialogue as a way of establishing value-semantic unity. According to the researcher, a full-fledged educational dialogue depends on three components:

- dialogicity of the teacher;
- dialogicity of educational material (as a fragment of the educational content under consideration);
- dialogicity of the student [10].

Another researcher, Y. Senko, claims that self-determination and self-development of both the teacher and the learner take place in dialogue, resulting in cooperative relationships and the achievement of common goals, mutual education and co-creation [15].

In fact, the implementation of dialogic communication in the process of professional training leads to the fact that the relationships that are formed between the subjects of education will contribute to self-actualization and self-development of the individual, which is a determining point in the formation of the future teacher-leader.

Dialogue in education is considered as a space for expanding human resources. Taken as a method, dialogue can be considered as an adequate and culturally expedient integrative humanitarian technology, which allows finding a personal resource, determining the possibilities of constructing a holistic personality formation in the educational process [11].

Domestic scientist V. Galuziak notes that educational dialogue is considered as a productive method of personal and professional development of future teachers. Dialogue takes place in the form of cognitive interaction between equal subjects, each of whom has the right to his own position. The author singled out the essential characteristics of dialogic educational interaction: openness, trust, recognition of the equality of personal positions, consideration by the teacher of the interests and needs of students, focus on the interlocutor, personal attitude of the teacher and students to information, personification of messages, which contributes to the joint search for truth and analysis of the results of interaction [1].

As noted by researchers N. Kuzmin, L. Petrovska, T. Yatsenko, educational dialogue, as a subject-subject communication, in its structure resembles social-psychological training and active social-psychological training. The role of dialogue in development the value-semantic sphere of personality was studied by O. Bondarevska, M. Kagan, Z. Karpenko, O. Klymyshyn, H. Radchuk, T. Florenska, M. Yanitsky, and others. An important factor in the dialogization of the educational environment is the dialogic culture of the teacher.

As a psychodidactic technology for the formation of leadership qualities in future teachers, we used an educational dialogue in the form of a development program.

So, thanks to the educational dialogue, as a form of active learning, it is possible to promote subject-subject interaction between the participants of the educational space. The dialogic form of education is the basis for building interpersonal contact, openness, trust, empathy, ensuring heuristics and problematic learning, critical thinking, development of creative potential and productive activity of all subjects of the educational environment [12].

The content of "dialogization" as a factor in the development of leadership qualities in future teachers consists, first of all, in promoting and facilitating the preparation of an assertive, active, reflective, open to new experience, capable of independent development and making non-standard decisions of the future teacher [15].

Taking into account the above and analyzing the psychological and pedagogical literature, we conclude that the educational dialogue is a partnership form of interaction, an effective method of obtaining knowledge and skills, new information, which makes it possible to timely and comprehensively check the skills and abilities acquired during joint activities and to apply these skills and skills in both educational and practical activities. The educational space is precisely the environment for the formation of the future specialist's personality.

Therefore, we assume that in order to promote the formation and development of leadership qualities and the activation of personal leadership potential in future teachers, in the process of professional training in a higher education institution, an appropriate psychoeducational program will be effective. Which combines methods aimed at self-knowledge and self-analysis, research of one's strengths and weaknesses, development of communication and emotional-regulatory skills, setting goals and achieving them, ability to work in a team, etc.

As part of the activities of the H. Radchuk Scientific School "Personality Development in the Context of Higher Professional Education" a psycho-educational program was developed and tested program in the form of an educational dialogue "New Faces of Leadership" for future teachers.

The training had a systematic, holistic, personally oriented character in accordance with the structure and purpose of the program for future teachers.

The concept of our psychoeducational program is based on the idea of the leadership qualities of the future teacher as an integrative and integral personality formation, formulated in the first chapter of our work. The created training program uses the achievements of domestic and foreign scientists, integrated elements of educational and psychoeducational development programs.

The goal of our psychoeducational program is to reveal the leadership potential of future teachers and develop the leadership qualities necessary for carrying out professional activities on the basis of partnership and humanization of education.

The main ones the tasks of our psycho-educational program "New Faces of Leadership" are outlined:

- 1) actualization of the processes of self-knowledge and self-analysis;
- 2) promoting awareness of one's own life and professional goals;
- 3) development of such personal leadership qualities as openness, flexibility, empathy, internality, communicativeness, creativity, reflexivity, motivation, self-organization;
- 4) development of emotional intelligence, positive self-esteem and reflective skills;
- 5) improving the skills of self-regulation of one's own behavior and the ability for self-development and self-education.

While developing the topics of classes and their content, we relied on the results of theoretical and scientific-practical explorations and empirical research. The structure of the development program contains a number of content modules. Therefore, according to its content, the lessons of the development program were combined into 4 modules:

- 1) "Development of self-knowledge and self-esteem."
- 2) "The structure of the image of "I am the leader"."
- 3) "Psychological principles of effective communication of a teacher-leader".
- 4) "Development of the emotional-regulatory ability of the individual".

The specified modules include a cycle of interconnected, logically structured classes held once a week. The structure of the development program included 12 thematic classes. The introductory and final classes were aimed at logically beginning and ending the entire cycle of classes and reflecting on the received information and acquired skills. After each class, training participants performed creative homework.

The method of carrying out the development program of the teacher's leadership qualities is based on the principle of phased development of the group and continuity in self-discovery and self-improvement. Each subsequent lesson is a logical continuation of the previous one, and in terms of content, it is the basis for the next one. In classes, it is important to create an emotionally comfortable, psychologically safe space so that participants can feel the influence of positive emotions and the desire to maintain and cultivate them.

Each lesson has a clear structure that includes the following components:

1) motivational and organizational – reflection by the participants of the previous lesson, analysis of homework, actualization of knowledge and experience on the subject of the lesson and formation of interest in it. In the introductory part of each lesson, short thematic stories-parables are offered; exercises to relieve emotional, physical and behavioral stiffness;

2) development of the emotional and personal sphere. The main part of the training is aimed at self-discovery of opportunities and limitations, emotional self-analysis; performing exercises for deepening emotional self-awareness, formation of skills to manage emotions, competence in time, positive thinking, social sensitivity, tolerance for others, assertiveness of behavior, readiness for cooperation and co-creation; development of personal authenticity, expressiveness and emotional expressiveness, increase of emotional freedom of participants, etc.;

3) reflexive At the final stage, summing up, discussion of work results, difficulties during class, as well as opportunities to apply the acquired experience in life are carried out. Exercise analysis and reflection include cognitive, emotional and behavioral components [3, 7, 8].

Each lesson was structured according to a logical scheme: greeting and clarifying the expectations of the participants from the lesson; dialogue between the participants and the trainer on the subject of the lesson; the telling of parables, the use of metaphors, which are one of the means of verbal visualization of the educational material, contribute to a better perception, visualization and understanding by the participants of its individual aspects, the development and consolidation of certain values and beliefs in them, awareness and recognition of the need to develop certain features of their personality; developmental exercises and exercises to develop certain abilities and skills; end of class

The following stages are distinguished in the structure of each lesson:

1. Greetings and clarifying the participants' expectations from the class. This is the creation of a favorable psychological climate for the work of the group and the coordination of the participants' expectations

before the start of the class. Such an approach helps to prepare participants for joint activities, brings the group together and allows the trainer to better understand the needs and moods of each participant.

Greeting exercises really help the participants to establish contact with each other and facilitate self-presentation, which can be especially useful in an unfamiliar group. Such exercises stimulate communication and strengthen interaction, as well as reduce tension and fear of new acquaintances.

Exercises on expressing expectations involve the active participation of participants, where everyone can freely share their wishes and expectations about the lesson. This allows each participant to feel important, heard and understood. In addition, such exercises help the trainer to navigate the needs of the group and to adjust the program of classes in such a way as to meet the expectations and needs of the participants as much as possible. Successful work with a group depends on the interaction between participants, because collective cooperation contributes to achieving better results. The introduction of psychological methods and techniques at the stage of greeting and expressing expectations creates a valuable foundation for further joint work and contributes to a positive experience for all group members.

Self-diagnosis is a method of self-discovery, awareness of one's own advantages and resources with the help of questions, exercises, and special methods.

2. Communication between the participants and the trainer on the subject of the lesson.

At this stage, the trainer introduces the subject of the lesson, outlines the main goals and tasks. Then the didactic part begins, which includes a discussion with the participants. To achieve the goals in this stage, the following forms and methods of work are used:

- educational dialogue: the use of this method allows you to present theoretical material related to the subject of the lesson to the participants. There is an expression of opinions and a discussion of the problems under consideration. Participants can share their ideas, points of view and analyze experiences;

- facilitation (from English to facilitate - the process of collective expression of opinions and solving tasks, where the leader plays the role of a facilitator, is an important element of training. The facilitator interacts with the participants, managing the process of discussion of issues, contributing to the establishment of constructive communication, directing them to find solutions and comply with the norms of interaction and regulations. During facilitation, the leader actively interacts with the group, asking questions that contribute to the activation of the group experience. It stimulates the exchange of information and experience between participants, supporting a constructive discussion. The facilitator also responds to each participant's statements, helping to elicit their opinions and encouraging active participation. At the beginning of a new topic, the facilitator invites each participant to briefly express their opinion on the question posed. After that, the host briefly summarizes what he heard, highlighting the most important points. During the discussion, the facilitator provides support for a constructive atmosphere

and helps to reconcile different views and approaches. At the end of the discussion, the presenter sums up and moves on to the theoretical part of the training. Facilitation helps to attract participants to active participation, promotes deeper assimilation of the material and development of critical thinking. It creates a favorable psychological climate for cooperation and joint activities of the group.

- use of parables and metaphors: the trainer can tell parables and use metaphors for a more visual representation of the learning material. These stories help participants better perceive and understand certain aspects of the topic, form values, beliefs and develop personal traits.

The use of such forms and methods of work helps to make the class more interesting, meaningful and contributes to better assimilation of the material by the participants. This approach encourages active participation, interaction and exchange of ideas between group members. In addition, it promotes the development of critical thinking and the perception of new ideas.

3. Carrying out development work on the subject of the lesson. At this stage of the class, correction and development of certain traits, qualities, individual psychological features, as well as skills and abilities of the participants is carried out. To achieve this goal, the following psychological methods and techniques are used:

- developmental exercises and exercises for the development of certain abilities and skills: these exercises contribute to the awareness of the importance of positive self-perception and the development of the skills of self-determination of individual characteristics. They help participants understand their strengths, work on weaknesses and achieve more harmonious development;

- creative work is exercises in which imagination is used as a means of training, for example: drawing, modeling, composing a composition, etc.

- role-playing method: This method involves "role-playing" where participants play certain social roles. This allows you to consider the behavior and attitude towards yourself and others through the prism of different roles. It promotes the development of empathy, analytical skills and the ability to cooperate;

- brainstorming method: using this method allows you to generate ideas and solutions with the participation of the whole group. Participants actively exchange their thoughts and ideas, which contributes to a broader consideration of the problem and finding creative solutions;

- mini-lectures and recommendations: The presenter can give mini-lectures and provide recommendations on optimizing certain personality traits and qualities or achieving self-created goals. It helps participants get practical advice and guidance to develop their skills and make personal changes;

- "aquarium" is a role-playing game in which several people participate, and others act as observers, that is, some "live" the situation, while others analyze the situation from the side and "empathize".

These methods and techniques contribute to the deep development of the participants, help to strengthen the positive sides of the personality and

work on self-improvement. They contribute to the creation of an atmosphere of support and understanding, which contributes to the positive development of each member of the group.

4. Completion of the lesson. This stage involves three points. At the final stage of the class, the following psychological methods and techniques are used:

- relaxation exercises these exercises help participants to relax and focus on their inner world. They contribute to deep introspection and reflection of various aspects of one's own life, which allows you to consolidate the positive effect of the lesson, establish emotional balance and relieve muscle tension;

- physical exercises : these exercises aim to end the class in a good mood, relieve emotional tension and psychologically relieve stress. They contribute to the creation of a positive emotional attitude towards the end of the class and contribute to raising the general mood of the participants;

- exercises-rituals: during these exercises, the results of the lesson are summed up, the results are analyzed and discussed with the participants. Participants have the opportunity to express their general impressions, share positive and negative moments, as well as express their wishes for further work;

- feedback, reflection. Most of the exercises involve the use of feedback to the presenter. The questions at the beginning of the exercise are asked in order to find out how familiar the participants are with the topic and to adjust them to the perception of new ideas and information. The questions at the end of the exercise are designed to find out the degree of assimilation of the material and its understanding. Effectively using the means of positive reinforcement - praise, positive evaluation, it is possible to significantly increase the self-esteem and motivation of the participants. Special exercises and questionnaires are used to establish feedback at the end of the training;

- sharing (eng . to share) is one of the final exercises of the class, which gives everyone present the opportunity to express their feelings, thoughts, impressions. Summary of the lesson;

- homework. After each class, the participants receive homework related to the application of emotional competences in real life.

These methods and techniques help to create a positive final accent of the lesson, consolidate the learning material and preserve the emotional satisfaction of participating in the lesson. They also help bring the group together and maintain a favorable psychological climate for the next class.

A feature of the first thematic block called "Development of self-knowledge and self-evaluation" was the promotion and teaching of methods of self-knowledge and research of one's "I". After all, without understanding the essence of one's personality, strengths and weaknesses, full-fledged development of the personality is impossible. The basis of any transformation is familiarization with one's own qualities, both positive and negative. This is the first step towards self-acceptance and self-development. Knowledge and understanding of oneself is the driving force of change. Therefore, the tasks, exercises and psychological workshops that were

used were mainly research-oriented and were aimed directly at the actualization of the processes of self-awareness and internal readiness for self-change .

The motivational and value block of the program is a key element aimed at the development of humanistic values of the future teacher. The exercises that were included in this block posed tasks to the participants that motivated them to present their life projects as best as possible in the context of their future profession, the manifestation of humanism and altruism.

These exercises contributed to the development and integration of national and professional values into the structure of personal values of future teachers . They directed the participants of the development program to act in the direction determined by these values, confirming and strengthening their significance. Thus, the formation of humanistic values contributed to the formation of a conscious attitude to the future professional activity, personality of the child. In addition, this block involved the development of achievement and affiliation motives. The exercises helped to find optimal situations for the development of one's own skills and abilities, and also taught to correctly analyze and evaluate the problem and one's possibilities for solving it. This helped the participants to enrich their motivation to achieve success and positive connections with others.

This approach contributes to the formation of deep values of the participants, ensures their development as responsible individuals capable of active activities in the interests of society

The purpose of the second module "Structure of the image of "I-leader" of our development program was to study the portrait of a modern teacher-leader. In the form of dialogue and discussions, outline and form a list of personal leadership qualities inherent in the professional image of the future teacher. The specifics of the classes consisted in the fact that game forms of work prevailed here, aimed at defining and discussing what qualities a pedagogue-leader should be endowed with. In the context of our research, it was important to find out that there are four components in the structure of leadership qualities (motivational-value, emotional-communicative, organizational-regulatory and reflective-evaluative). During the work, the participants had the opportunity to analyze personal experience, real life situations, which are analyzed by the group. In addition, the exercises of the " I-leader image structure " block were aimed at developing self-acceptance and self-understanding , as this is the basis of self-confidence. Some exercises taught to think rationally, to build logical chains, which ultimately led to the search for the optimal solution to each specific problem that may be faced by the leader.

The third thematic module " Psychological principles of effective communication of a teacher-leader " was aimed at research and development of effective communication skills . During the classes, future teachers had the opportunity to understand and rethink the phenomenon of dialogue, to discuss the importance of effective communication in the educational space, about dialogue as a driving condition for the formation of a full-fledged personality. The exercises helped to

practice the skills of effective communication, assertive behavior, develop emotional intelligence, skills of reflective analysis of one's own professional capabilities . was aimed at developing the skills of effective communication, communicative control. The exercises helped to show assertiveness , take the position of another person, choose a conversation style according to each interlocutor, approach each situation individually, determine one's own strengths and strategies of behavior in accordance with one's own needs, goals and expected results of the ongoing dialogue, as well as take into account interests others, recognize the interlocutor's emotions and predict his reactions to some of his own words, gestures and behavior.

The fourth block, entitled " Development of the emotional and regulatory ability of the individual ", involved learning and improving the skills of self-control and self-regulation of one's own behavior, actualization of the processes of self-improvement and self-actualization. With the help of exercises and techniques, the participants were able to explore their emotional state and that of their interlocutor, take it into account during communication, and also develop the skills of empathy and reflexivity . In developed self-regulation, it is important to single out skills that ensure a positive transformation of the student's attitude to himself, to activities and communication, to the surrounding world as a whole. That is, we are talking about the ability to control and correct one's own behavior; the ability to show will in achieving a goal; the ability to choose effective means of behavior and interaction with the surrounding people.

Emotional -regulatory qualities involve the ability and skills of self-understanding and self-mastery , first of all, in the emotional plan. This can be achieved by performing exercises aimed at identifying and defining one's own emotions, their causes and consequences, and then understanding the emotions of others, which is very important for a socially active person. Therefore, exercises aimed at teaching how to recognize the state of stress and social frustration , master them, use adequate coping strategies, reduce negative emotional manifestations and prevent the negative consequences of stress were selected. Also, to reduce the level of frustration and anxiety, exercises were used that teach you to trust others, tell your feelings and problems in search of support where needed.

The following interactive methods were used in our psychoeducational development program:

- "brain storming" or the "brainstorming" method (individual, "pair" and group options);
- method of incomplete sentences (with subsequent group discussion);
- filling out worksheets (studying expectations; revealing the content of the main concepts of the topic, etc.);
- execution of creative tasks (projects) and their presentation in the form of diagrams, drawings, etc.;
- "case method" or analysis of situations (discussion of "real" problem situations that arise in pedagogical activity and search for optimal options for their solution);
- "aquarium";

- role games;
- intergroup discussions (presentation by working groups of the results of certain tasks; asking clarifying and problematic questions; answers to the questions, etc.);
- psychological workshop (performance of diagnostic tasks; their analysis and discussion at the group level);
- performing homework (performance of individual tasks, using "specific" examples of social activity based on the activity material of a specific educational institution);
- sharing _
- lesson reflection (individual; group).

The main principles that guided us in conducting classes were:

- principle of activity
- the principle of responsibility;
- the principle of humanism;
- the principle of confidentiality;
- principle of competence;
- personifications of expressions:
- the principle of dialogization of interaction

Thus, the psychoeducational program "New Faces of Leadership" for the development of leadership qualities of future teachers was developed taking into account all the principles and requirements for conducting corrective and developmental work and contributed to the harmonization of professional and personal development, personal growth and actualization of leadership qualities of future teachers. A clear structure of the psycho-educational program was determined, which is a holistic tool for the development of personal qualities necessary for a teacher-leader. The psychoeducational program was developed by us taking into account all the principles and requirements for conducting developmental work and contributed to the actualization of the processes of self-knowledge, the harmonization of professional and personal growth and the development of leadership qualities in future teachers .

Indicators of the effectiveness of the psychoeducational program can be the following key aspects:

1). Achievements of the participants: the volume of acquired knowledge and competences acquired during the training are evaluated. It also includes changes in beliefs, emotional responses, behavior and personal development.

2). Results of motivational control: participants' progress is assessed at the end of each session. Special exercises or tasks are used to check mastery of the material and understanding of key concepts.

3). The quality of homework: the quality and timeliness of homework is evaluated, which helps to strengthen and consolidate the acquired knowledge and skills.

4). Positive reaction of the participants: questionnaires, surveys and interviews are used to find out about the satisfaction of the participants with the training and their positive impressions.

5). The results of self-diagnosis and testing: the progress of the participants before and after the training is evaluated with the help of special tests and self-diagnosis.

6). Evaluation of personal changes by others: the "360-degree method" is used, where colleagues, teachers, relatives, etc. evaluate the changes of the participants and the impact of the training on their behavior and relationships with others.

These indicators help determine the effectiveness of the program, assess its impact on participants and implement the necessary adjustments to improve results.

Conclusions. Therefore, the educational environment of a higher education institution is designed to promote the formation and development of leadership qualities of future teachers. Thus, dialogue is an important subject of discussion and analysis for modern education, as it is one of the most important elements of humanitarian paradigms in education. We believe that educational institutions should be a so-called school of leadership. After all, first of all, teachers must possess certain leadership qualities and must be ready for subject-subject relationships with students and dialogization of the educational process. The educational space is designed to be the environment in which self-sufficient personalities are formed and developed thanks to subject-subject interaction. After all, it is the youth age that is sensitive to the development of the value -meaning sphere of the individual, reflection, awareness of individuality and one's own "I". We see the prospect of further research in the further implementation of a psycho-educational development program of leadership qualities among future teachers and the use of educational dialogue as an effective psychological and pedagogical technology for the development of leadership qualities in the process of professional training in a higher education institution.

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